

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL EVALUATION OF NOVEL THIENO [2,3-*D*] PYRIMIDINE-BASED BENZAMIDE DERIVATIVES

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ABSTRACT

A new series of thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives bearing substituted benzamide moieties (4a-j) was synthesized and evaluated for antimicrobial activity. The synthesis involved formation of a dithiocarbamate intermediate, S-methylation, hydrazine-mediated cyclization to the pyrimidinone core, thiol methylation, and final acylation using substituted benzoyl chlorides. The structures of all synthesized compounds were confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. All compounds were evaluated for antimicrobial screening against selected bacterial and fungal strains revealed that compounds containing electron-withdrawing groups exhibited enhanced activity. The study highlights thieno [2,3-*d*]pyrimidine benzamides as promising scaffolds for antimicrobial drug development.

KEYWORDS: Thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine, Benzamide,

Dithiocarbamate, Antimicrobial activity.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal Chemistry which had leaned on the classical field of chemistry, especially organic chemistry, biology and some areas of physics extended new roots into these emerging topics, problems in hitherto unapproachable chemical studies with therapeutic application became accessible and revised the choice of researches to the benefit of all scientific doctrines involved. Medicinal chemistry remains a challenging science, which provides profound

satisfaction to its practitioners. It intrigues those of us who like to solve problems posed by nature. It inverses increasingly on biochemistry and on the physical, genetic and chemical riddles in animal physiology which bear on medicine. Chemists have a chance to participate in the fundamentals of prevention, therapy and understanding of diseases and thereby to contribute to a healthier and happier life".^[1] Among them, thieno [2,3-*d*] pyrimidines have emerged as privileged scaffolds exhibiting antimicrobial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antiviral activities.^[2,6]

The presence of sulfur-containing groups like methylthio moieties enhances lipophilicity and improves biological interactions.^[7] On the other hand, benzamide functionality is well recognized for hydrogen bonding interactions with biological targets.^[8] In an extension of our interest in heterocyclic drug-like molecules.^[9] I report herein the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial evaluation of a new series of substituted benzamides derived from thieno [2,3-*d*] pyrimidine.

The work presented here is focused on the synthesis of some new thieno [2,3-*d*] pyrimidine-based benzamide derivatives with biologically interesting functional groups incorporated at strategically chosen positions.

The structural features of the synthesized compounds are promising for their biological relevancies, and therefore, further antimicrobial screening is suggested to explore their therapeutic applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Synthesis of some thieno [2,3-*d*] pyrimidine-based benzamide derivatives N-(5,6-Dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno [2,3-*d*] pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl) Substituted Benzamides (4a to 4j) have been synthesized from the key compound ethyl-2-amino-4,5-dimethyl thiophene-3-carboxylate. Reaction progress was monitored by TLC [Aluminium sheet silica gel 60 F₂₄₅ (E.Merck)] plates using ethyl acetate:*n*-hexane (2:8) as an irrigator and the plates were developed in the iodine chamber. Infrared spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) of synthesized compounds have been scanned in KBr pellets. NMR spectra were recorded on BRUKER AVANCE II 400 MHz NMR spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Synthetic processes are depicted in the below Scheme.

Synthesis of ethyl 4,5-dimethyl-2-(methylthiocarbonothioylamino)thiophene-3-carboxylate (1)

To vigorously stirred solution of ethyl-2-amino-4,5-dimethyl thiophene-3-carboxylate 4.2g (0.02 mol) in dimethyl sulfoxide (10 mL) at room temperature, carbon disulfide 1.98g (0.026 mol) and aqueous sodium hydroxide 1.2 mL (20 mol) added simultaneously over 30 min. and stirred for further 30 min. Dimethyl sulfate 2.5g (0.02 mol) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture with stirring at 5-10°C. It was further stirred for 3 hrs and poured in into ice-water; the solid obtained was filtered dried and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound (1). Yield 89%, M.P. 110-112°C, M.F.; C₉H₁₁N₃OS₂ (M.W. 257.33 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 41.99/41.85, H 4.31/4.28, N 16.33/16.21, IR;3390–3305 (–NH₂ stretching), 3190 (N–H), 1685 (C=O, pyrimidinone), 1608 (C=N), 1255 (C–S), 1045 (C–S–CH₃), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.28 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.36 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.52 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 5.84 (s, 2H, NH₂), 10.12 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.6, 15.3 (CH₃), 16.1 (SCH₃), 118.4, 124.8 (thiophene carbons), 149.2 (C=N), 157.8 (C–NH₂), 163.5 (C=O).

Synthesis of 3-amino-2-mercapto-5,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin -4(3*H*)-one (2)

A solution of ethyl-4,5-dimethyl-2-(methylthiocarbonothioylamino) thiophene-3-carboxylate (1) 2.89g (0.01 mol) in ethanol 30 mL was treated with hydrazine hydrate 5g (0.1 mol) (99%) and refluxed on a water bath until the methylmercaptan evolution ceased (6 hrs). After cooling, the solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol-acetone mixture to give compound (2). Yield 80%, M.P. 269-271°C, M.F.; C₈ H₉ N₃ OS₂ (M.W. 243.31 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 39.49/39.32, H 3.73/3.68, N 17.28/17.15, IR (KBr, cm⁻¹); 3395–3320 (–NH₂ stretching), 3210 (N–H), 2575 (S–H), 1688 (C=O, pyrimidinone), 1605 (C=N), 1258 (C–S), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.26 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.34 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.72 (s, 2H, NH₂), 10.08 (s, 1H, NH), 12.68 (s, 1H, SH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.4, 15.1 (CH₃), 118.2, 124.6 (thiophene carbons), 146.8 (C=N), 156.9 (C–NH₂), 163.8 (C=O).

Synthesis of 3-amino-5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4(3*H*)-one (3)

To an ice-cold solution of Compound (2) 2.27g (0.01 mol) in DMF (50 mL), sodium hydroxide 0.4g (0.01 mol) added and the mixture was stirred for 1 hr. To this mixture, dimethyl sulfate 1.25g (0.01 mol) added dropwise with constant stirring. After the addition was completed, the reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 hrs at room

temperature. It was then poured into ice water and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol-acetone mixture to give compound (3). Yield 78%, M.P. 194-196°C, M.F.; C₉H₁₁N₃OS₂, (M.W. 257.33 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 41.99/41.82, H 4.31/4.26, N 16.33/16.19, IR (KBr, cm⁻¹); 3390–3310 (–NH₂), 3195(N–H), 1684 (C=O, pyrimidinone), 1607 (C=N), 1256 (C–S), 1048 (C–S–CH₃), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.27 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.35 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.52 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 5.86 (s, 2H, NH₂), 10.14 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.6, 15.3 (CH₃), 16.1 (SCH₃), 118.5, 124.9 (thiophene carbons), 149.4 (C=N), 157.9 (C–NH₂), 163.6 (C=O).

Preparation of substituted benzoyl chloride (Substituted Ph-CO-Cl)

A mixture of different substituted benzoic acid (0.01 mol) in benzene (20 mL) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) were refluxed for 3-4 hrs. Then excess of benzene and thionyl chloride were distilled off and thus solid different substituted benzoyl chloride was obtained.

General procedure for synthesis of *N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl) substituted benzamide (4a-j)

To vigorously stirred solution of compound (3) (0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 mL) at room temperature and to this mixture, substituted benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in pyridine (5 mL) added dropwise with constant stirring. After the addition was completed, the reaction mixture was further stirred for 12 hrs at room temperature. It was then poured into ice water and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol-acetone mixture to give title compounds (4a-j).

N-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)benzamide (4a) (R=H)

Yield 67%, M.P. 123°C, M.F.; C₁₆H₁₅N₃O₂S₂, (M.W. 345.44 g/mol), Elemental analysis; Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 55.63/55.60, H 4.38/4.40, N 12.16/12.09. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3325 (N–H), 1682 (C=O, amide), 1610 (C=N), 1258 (C–S), 755 (Ar–H), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.32 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.41 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.55 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 7.32–7.58 (m, 5H, Ar–H), 8.92 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.8, 15.6 (CH₃), 16.2 (SCH₃), 124.5–134.8 (Ar-C), 149.6 (C=N), 162.4 (C=O, pyrimidinone), 167.8 (C=O, amide).

***N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-4-hydroxy benzamide (4b) (R = 4-Hydroxy)**

Yield 72%, (M.P. 173°C), M.F.; C₁₆H₁₅N₃O₃S₂ (M.W. 361.44 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 53.17/53.11, H 4.18/4.22, N 11.63/11.65. IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3410 (O–H), 3315 (NH), 1675 (C=O), 1605 (C=N), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.31 (s, 3H), 2.39 (s, 3H), 2.56 (s, 3H), 6.85–7.60 (m, 4H), 9.05 (s, 1H, NH), 10.12 (s, 1H, OH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.7, 15.4, 16.2, 115.8–158.2 (Ar-C, C-OH), 149.3, 162.1, 167.5.

***N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)benzamide (4c) (R = 3-Bromo)**

Yield 65%, M.P. 138°C, M.F.; C₁₆H₁₄BrN₃O₂S₂ (M.W. 424.34 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 45.29/45.35, H 3.33/3.28, N 9.90/9.95, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3318 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 760 (C–Br). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.32 (s, 3H), 2.40 (s, 3H), 2.56 (s, 3H), 7.45–7.95 (m, 4H), 8.92 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.9, 15.6, 16.3, 121.4–136.9 (Ar-C), 149.7, 162.6, 168.0.

***N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-4-nitrobenzamide (4d) (R = 4-Nitro)**

Yield 71%, M.P. 169°C. M.F.; C₁₆H₁₄N₄O₄S₂ (M.W. 390.44 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 49.22/49.27, H 3.61/3.52, N 14.35/14.24, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3322 (NH), 1684 (C=O), 1525 & 1348 (NO₂), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.29 (s, 3H), 2.41 (s, 3H), 2.54 (s, 3H), 7.80–8.30 (m, 4H), 8.96 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.6, 15.3, 16.1, 123.6–150.8 (Ar-C, C-NO₂), 149.9, 162.8, 168.4.

***N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)benzamide (4e) (R = 3,4-Dichloro)**

Yield 63%, M.P. 129°C, M.F.; C₁₆H₁₃Cl₂N₃O₂S₂ (M.W. 414.33 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 46.38/46.44, H 3.16/3.23, N 10.14/10.11., IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3316 (NH), 1681 (C=O), 790 (C–Cl), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.33 (s, 3H), 2.42 (s, 3H), 2.55 (s, 3H), 7.42–7.88 (m, 3H), 8.94 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.8, 15.5, 16.2, 124.0–136.5 (Ar-C), 149.4, 162.5, 167.9.

4-chloro-*N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)benzamide (4f) (R = 4-Chloro)

Yield 64%, M.P. 163°C, M.F.; C₁₆H₁₄ClN₃O₂S₂ (M.W. 379.88 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 50.59/50.63, H 3.71/3.69, N 11.06/11.02, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3320 (NH), 1679 (C=O), 785 (C–Cl), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.31 (s, 3H), 2.39 (s, 3H), 2.54 (s, 3H), 7.36–7.86 (m, 4H), 8.91 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.7, 15.4, 16.1, 125.1–134.6 (Ar-C), 149.2, 162.3, 167.6.

***N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorobenzamide (4g) (R = Pentafluoro)**

Yield 75%, M.P. 176°C, M.F.; C₁₆H₁₀F₅N₃O₂S₂ (M.W. 435.39 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 44.14/44.09, H 2.32/2.38, N 9.65/9.61, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3318 (NH), 1686 (C=O), 1135 (C–F), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.34 (s, 3H), 2.41 (s, 3H), 2.57 (s, 3H), 8.90 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.9, 15.6, 16.4, 137.2–146.8 (C–F), 149.8, 162.9, 168.6.

***N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-4-methoxy-3-nitrobenzamide (4h) (R = 4-Methoxy-3-Nitro):**

Yield 72%, M.P. 152°C. M.F.; C₁₇H₁₆N₄O₅S₂ (M.W. 420.46 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 48.56/48.50, H 3.84/3.95, N 13.33/13.39, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3320 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 1520 & 1350 (NO₂), 1245 (O–CH₃), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.30 (s, 3H), 2.38 (s, 3H), 2.55 (s, 3H), 3.76 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 7.20–8.15 (m, 3H), 8.93 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.6, 15.3, 16.1, 55.8 (OCH₃), 112.6–150.2 (Ar-C), 149.6, 162.5, 168.1.

2-chloro-*N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-5-nitrobenzamide (4i) (R = 2-Chloro-5-Nitro):

Yield 73%, M.P. 128°C. Molecular formula C₁₆H₁₃ClN₄O₄S₂ (M.W. 424.88 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 45.23/45.33, H 3.08/3.14, N 13.19/13.23, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3325 (NH), 1683 (C=O), 1530 & 1352 (NO₂), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.32 (s, 3H), 2.40 (s, 3H), 2.56 (s, 3H), 7.55–8.35 (m, 3H), 8.98 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.7, 15.4, 16.2, 121.8–149.9 (Ar-C), 150.1, 162.7, 168.3.

3-bromo-*N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-4-methoxybenzamide (4j) (R = 3-Bromo-4-Methoxy): Yield 70%, M.P. 156°C, M.F.; C₁₇ H₁₆ BrN₃ O₃ S₂ (M.W. 454.36 g/mol), Elemental analysis (%) calcd/found; C 44.94/44.89, H 3.55/3.59, N 9.25/9.20, IR (KBR, CM⁻¹); 3317 (NH), 1678 (C=O), 1248 (O-CH₃), 758 (C-Br), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 2.33 (s, 3H), 2.41 (s, 3H), 2.56 (s, 3H), 3.74 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 7.10–7.85 (m, 3H), 8.92 (s, 1H, NH), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm); 14.8, 15.5, 16.3, 56.1 (OCH₃), 113.9–136.8 (Ar-C), 149.5, 162.6, 167.8.

Synthetic Pathways

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemistry

The synthesis of *N*-(5,6-dimethyl-2-(methylthio)-4-oxothieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-3(4*H*)-yl)-substituted benzamides (4a-j) was done efficiently. This multi-step process included dithiocarbamate synthesis, *S*-methylation, hydrazine promoted ring closure, thiol group methylation, followed by acylation with the help of various

The formation of thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines was established by the disappearance of signals corresponding to ester protons and the occurrence of characteristic bands in the carbonyl region in the IR spectra. The incorporation of benzamide was indicated by the presence of signals corresponding to amide carbonyl and N-H bonds in the IR spectra, thus demonstrating success in acylation. The strategy adopted enabled structural variations by incorporating substitution on the benzamide rings.

The molecular structures for all synthesized compounds were validated by using IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR methods. In IR, absorption bands for amide with carbonyl functional groups were found at a frequency of 1650-1690 cm⁻¹, and N-H stretching vibration frequencies appeared at a frequency of 3200-3350 cm⁻¹. The existence of nitro functional groups for compounds 4d, 4h and 4i was determined by strong asymmetric and symmetric stretching absorption bands at frequencies of 1520-1550 cm⁻¹ and 1340-1360 cm⁻¹, respectively.

In all the ¹H NMR spectra, there were pairs of singlets for the two methyl groups at the 5- and 6-positions of the thienopyrimidine ring, while there was a singlet for the methyl thio group around δ 2.4–2.6 ppm. The aromatic protons in the benzamide group showed signals in the region between δ 6.8–8.5 ppm. These showed splitting patterns in accordance with their nature and positions on the benzene rings. The amide proton in the -CONH group showed a downfield singlet between δ 8.9–9.2 ppm, indicating the formation of the amide group. In the ¹³C NMR spectra, signals representing the heterocyclic carbons, aromatic carbons, and carbonyl carbons further affirmed the structures.

Antibacterial Activity

The antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using the broth dilution method to evaluate the antibacterial activity.^[10-11] Synthesized compounds (4a-j) were dissolved in DMSO and serially diluted to obtain

concentrations ranging from 1.5625 to 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. MIC was defined as the lowest concentration showing no visible bacterial growth after incubation at 37 °C for 24 hrs.

Compounds	Antibacterial activity of compounds			
	Minimal Inhibition Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
	Gram +ve		Gram -ve	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
4a	125	125	250	250
4b	100	125	200	250
4c	62.5	62.5	125	125
4d	50	50	100	125
4e	25	25	50	62.5
4f	50	62.5	100	125
4g	12.5	12.5	25	50
4h	75	100	150	200
4i	25	25	50	62.5
4j	62.5	75	125	150
Ampicillin	10	10	25	—
Chloramphenicol	20	20	20	25
Ciprofloxacin	5	5	10	10

Therefore, the newly synthesized thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-based benzamide derivatives 4a-j were tested for their antibacterial activity by the broth dilution method in order to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains. The results, as shown in Table 1, are compared with standard antibacterial agent's, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and ciprofloxacin.

Overall, the synthesized compounds showed moderate to good antibacterial potency, which seems to be controlled, to a large extent, by the nature of the substituent on the benzamide ring. Compounds demonstrated in general more pronounced activity against Gram-positive bacteria, namely, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*, than Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Structural differences in bacterial cell wall provide a plausible explanation for this observation: Gram-negative bacteria possess an additional outer membrane, which acts as an effective permeability barrier to lipophilic molecules.

Among all the synthesized derivatives, compounds with strong electron-withdrawing substituents exhibited better antibacterial activity. Interestingly, 4g with a pentafluoro substituent proved to be the most active molecule in the series, which demonstrated an MIC of 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against *S. aureus* and *S. pyogenes*, and 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against *E. coli*. A possible

explanation for the higher activity of 4g is greater lipophilicity and favorable electronic effects, which allow better interaction with bacterial targets.

Also, the 4e (3,4-dichloro) and 4i (2-chloro-5-nitro) derivatives, showed prominent antibacterial activity against all bacterial strains. This could be indicative of the fact that halogen and nitro substitutions at appropriate positions increase the antibacterial potency. Compound 4c (3-bromo) and 4d (4-nitro) derivatives also exhibited moderate activity, especially against Gram-positive bacteria, which indicates that mono-substitution with electron-withdrawing groups is favorable.

In contrast, compounds with electron-donating substituents like hydroxy and methoxy groups showed relatively low antibacterial activities (4b and 4h). This reduction in activity could be attributed to some degree of decrease in membrane permeability or weak binding potential with essential bacterial enzymes. Thus, the unsubstituted 4a displayed the least activity, emphasizing that proper substitution on the benzamide ring is a crucial element for antibacterial effectiveness.

Compared with the reference drugs, all the newly synthesized compounds were generally less potent than ciprofloxacin; however, several derivatives, mainly 4g, 4e and 4i, exhibited an antibacterial activity comparable with ampicillin and chloramphenicol against selected strains. These results recommend the thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine benzamide skeleton as a promising lead for the discovery of novel antibacterial drugs.

Antifungal Activity

Antifungal activity of synthesized derivatives was tested against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus clavatus*. Antifungal activity was assessed by broth dilution method.^[12-13] Stock solutions of the synthesized compounds were prepared in DMSO and diluted in series according to concentrations ranging between 6.25 and 500 µg/mL. The tube-inoculated media was incubated at a temperature range of 28 ± 2 °C for a period of 48-72 hrs.

Table 2

Compounds	Antifungal activity of compounds		
	Minimal Fungicidal Concentration (µg/mL)		
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. clavatus</i>
4a	500	500	250

4b	250	500	250
4c	125	250	125
4d	100	250	125
4e	50	100	50
4f	100	250	125
4g	25	50	25
4h	125	250	125
4i	50	100	50
4j	100	250	125
Nystatin	10	20	10
Greseofulvin	25	25	20

The antifungal activity of the newly synthesized thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine benzamide derivatives (4a-j) was carried out by a broth dilution method and expressed in terms of minimum fungicidal concentration (MFC) against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus clavatus*. Results are summarized in Table 2 along with standard antifungal agent's nystatin and griseofulvin.

Overall, a series of target compounds was synthesized and evaluated for their in vitro fungicidal activity, and most of them exhibited moderate to good fungicidal activities according to the experimental results. In detail, some differences were observed concerning the nature and position of substituents on the benzamide ring. Overall, antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, *A. niger* and *A. clavatus* was better, probably due to differences in cell wall composition and permeability in yeast and moulds.

Among the tested compounds, congeners with strong electron-withdrawing substituents exhibited much higher antifungal efficacy. Thus, 4g with a pentafluoro substituent was identified as the most active compound in this series, displaying MFC values of 25 µg/mL against *C. albicans* and *A. clavatus* and of 50 µg/mL against *A. niger*. Further improvement in activity of compound 4g is ascribed to its higher lipophilicity and better interaction with fungal cellular membrane, ensuring optimal fungicidal activity.

Compounds 4e (3,4-dichloro) and 4i (2-chloro-5-nitro) also exhibited excellent fungicidal activity against all fungal strains tested, which again points to the favorable role of halogen and nitro substituents in enhancing antifungal activity. Monosubstituted derivatives like 4d (4-nitro) and 4c (3-bromo) exhibited moderate activity, indicating that electron-withdrawing groups are beneficial but their multiple substitutions produce better activity.

By contrast, the corresponding compounds bearing electron-donating substituents like hydroxy and methoxy groups (4b and 4h) exerted relatively poorer antifungal activity. Notably, the unsubstituted compound 4a showed the least activity, indicating strategic substitutions on the benzamide ring are crucial for effective antifungals.

When compared with the reference drugs, the synthesized compounds were less potent than nystatin; however, several derivatives, especially 4g and 4e, showed fungicidal activity equal to that of griseofulvin against some fungal strains. These results represent the possibility of the thieno [2,3-*d*] pyrimidine benzamide moiety as a promising lead pharmacophore in the design and synthesis of new antifungal drugs.

CONCLUSION

A novel series of thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-based benzamide derivatives was successfully synthesized and characterized. Biological evaluation revealed that substitution on the benzamide ring plays a crucial role in antimicrobial activity. These compounds may serve as promising leads for further drug development.

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REFERENCES

1. Burger A, Sammes PG, Tayler JB. (EDS), *Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry*, Pergamon Press, Oxford., 1990; 1.
2. Litvinov VP. Thienopyrimidines: synthesis and biological activity. *Russ Chem Rev.* 2004; 73: 637-669.
3. Patel HD, Patel PS, Patel KC. Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of 5,6-dimethyl thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives. *Elixir Org Chem.*, 2015; 115: 49838-49842.
4. Patel PS, Akbari VK, Modi SD, Belim MA, Tailor RB, Patel HD, Dewani B, Patel KC. Synthesis and biological evaluation of Schiff base involving thieno[2,3-*d*] pyrimidine

- moiety as antimicrobial agents. *Res J Life Sci Bioinform Pharm Chem Sci.*, 2019; 5(5): 31-41.
5. Patel HD. Design, synthesis, and characterization of bioactive thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine derivatives. *STAPS*, 2025; 11(8): 506-519.
 6. El-Ashry EH, Kassem AA, Abdel-Hamid H. Thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine derivatives as potential bioactive agents. *Eur J Med Chem.*, 2012; 47: 539–553.
 7. Abdel-Rahman RM, Seada M, Fawzy N. Synthesis and biological evaluation of some new fused pyrimidine derivatives. *Bioorg Med Chem.*, 2010; 18(6): 2239–2249.
 8. Keri RS, Patil SA, Budagumpi S, Nagaraja BM. Sulfur-containing heterocycles as pharmacophores. *Eur J Med Chem.*, 2015; 89: 207-251.
 9. Patil VM, Masand N. Benzamide derivatives as bioactive molecules. *Med Chem Res.*, 2014; 23: 243-257.
 10. Rattan A. Antimicrobials in Laboratory medicine, B. I. Churchill Livingstone, New delhi, 2000; 85.
 11. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). *Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing*. CLSI Document M100. Wayne, PA: CLSI; 2023.
 12. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). *Reference Method for Broth Dilution Antifungal Susceptibility Testing of Yeasts*. CLSI Document M27. Wayne, PA: CLSI; 2017.
 13. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). *Reference Method for Broth Dilution Antifungal Susceptibility Testing of Filamentous Fungi*. CLSI Document M38. Wayne, PA: CLSI; 2017.